

Hydrogen rich products from waste HDPE/LDPE/PP/PET over Me/Ni-ZSM-5 catalysts combined with dolomite

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ABSTRACT

This work focuses on the pyrolysis-gasification of real waste polymers in one stage tubular reactor with and without catalyst at 550 °C and 850 °C. Moreover, the possibility for dry reforming by in situ CO₂ generation was also investigated using dolomite. To enhance the syngas production from waste plastics, Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst was synthesized by wet impregnation with 4.82% of Ni, then the catalyst was loaded by further elements in ~2% concentration (Ca, Ce, La, Mg, and Mn). The composition of gases and liquid products was measured by gas-chromatography, while the coke deposition on the spent catalysts was followed by temperature-programmed oxidation. It was found that a large amount of amorphous carbons was produced at 550 °C with Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst. The in-situ addition of the carbon-dioxide can enhance the production of syngas because both the hydrogen and carbon-monoxide concentration can drastically increase. Furthermore, the carbon deposition on the catalyst surface can be reduced by using dolomite. Based on the results of the various Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts, the Ce/Ni/ZSM-5 was the most promising catalyst for the production of syngas (122.6 mmol/g at 850 °C). While, Mg/Ni/ZSM-5 showed less effect on the decomposition reaction, as low syngas yield was produced (62.8 mmol/g at 850 °C). The maximum yield of pyrolysis oil was achieved at 550 °C for the process without the catalyst.

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1. Introduction

Plastics have been used widely in domestic and industrial applications due to their low cost, versatility, durability, and easy manufacturing [1,2]. Furthermore, plastics are comparatively light and cheap materials. The dramatic increase in plastics waste, as a result of high consumption, caused a serious environmental problems [3]. Some difficulties are facing the disposal of plastic wastes because they are non-biodegradable and have high chemical resistance. Plastic wastes are mainly composed of polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate, polystyrene, and polyvinyl chloride [4]. On the other hand, there are some drawbacks in the using of conventional techniques for plastic wastes recycling, due to the presence of contaminants and impurities. Hence, the researchers are in a continuous quest to develop novel techniques to recycle or reuse the waste plastic.

Waste to energy processes are considered as one of the possible

attractive ways for plastic waste recycling and converting the polymeric materials into valuable products such as hydrogen [5]. Pyrolysis process is an example of the technologies which can save the environment by reducing the amount of plastics waste. Gases, oil, and char are the main products of the pyrolysis. However, there are some key factors that affect the pyrolysis products (product compositions) such as temperature, catalyst type, feedstock, flow rate, and type of carrier gas [6]. Higher temperatures are favoured for the C–C, C–H, C–X decomposition reaction during the process. High temperature can decrease the amount of liquids and wax-like residue in the product yields and can be resulting in more significant cracking of long carbon chains. Therefore, pyrolysis is considered an attractive technique towards plastic waste management and renewable energy production [7,8].

Hydrogen and syngas can be produced by the thermal conversion of plastic waste in the presence of catalysts. Different types of metals with different supports such as ZSM-5, natural zeolite, and alumina have been examined in the pyrolysis process to improve and enhance the products [9–11]. The catalysts have the ability to increase the cracking rate of long-chain polymers and resulting in high production of gases and oil yields. The presence of a catalyst in

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pyrolysis process can minimize the activation energy and improve the conversion rate [12,13]. Additionally, catalysts have also a positive effect on the pyrolysis products through decreasing the halogen concentration in the oil produced [14]. Bimetallic catalysts such as Ni, Co, Cu, and Fe have been investigated in the decomposition of plastics waste. These catalysts promoted the pyrolysis reactions [15]. Moreover, they are relatively cheap and they can reduce the amount of coke formation through the pyrolysis process [16]. Among all catalyst supports, ZSM-5 has been widely used in the pyrolysis process due to its ability to improve the hydrocarbon composition of products. Using of ZSM-5 catalyst as support for Ni can minimize the agglomeration that caused catalyst deactivation [17]. However, many researchers have investigated the effects of Ni on zeolite catalysts for the thermal decomposition reaction. Yung et al. [18] studied the effect of Ni loaded catalysts on pyrolysis of biomass. In another work Teh et al. [19] studied the performance of Ni/ZSM-5 for carbon monoxide methanation. They found that the structure of ZSM-5 has a synergistic effect due to its micro-mesoporosity and basicity existence which improved the catalyst performance. Moreover, the structure and uniformity for nickel-based catalyst particles can be improved by the addition of promoters which led to better dispersion of metal and resulting in more syngas yield from the dry reforming process [20]. However, there is a lack of information about the role of second metal promoters in the decomposition reaction of waste plastic in the presence of dolomite. Moreover, the information about the combined use of promoters with nickel is still limited.

In this research, real waste plastics were pyrolyzed-gasified at 550 °C and 850 °C in a one-stage tubular reactor. The influences of various bimetallic catalysts and pyrolysis temperature on the syngas production and product yields were investigated. Additionally, the production of syngas with a different carrier gas (N₂ and CO₂) was investigated, especially the possibility for in-situ CO₂ generation as sufficient atmosphere to dry reforming.

2. Experimental

2.1. Raw materials

Mixtures of real waste plastics were used as raw materials obtained from municipal waste containers: 14% high-density polyethylene, 17% low-density polyethylene, 19% polypropylene, 45% polyethylene terephthalate, and 5% others (e.g. polystyrene, ethylene-propylene copolymer). The composition of raw material was identified by the FTIR method (Bruker Tensor 27 instrument) based on the infrared spectra of waste plastic particles. According to proximate and ultimate analyses, raw materials had 72% carbon, 11% hydrogen and 16% oxygen, and 1% nitrogen content. The moisture and ash content was 1.1% and 2.4%, respectively.

2.2. Catalysts

In our present work, bimetallic catalysts have been synthesized and tested to affect the product quantity and composition, especially increasing in synthesis gas yield. Firstly, the neat ZSM-5 synthetic zeolite catalyst supporter was loaded with nickel by wet impregnation (1M Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O), then the produced Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst was calcined at 650 °C for 5 h in the air. The neat ZSM-5 catalyst had a 51.5 Si/Al ratio and 551 m²/g BET (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller) surface area. The bimetallic Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts were prepared by the following method. CaCl₂, CeSO₄·4H₂O, LaCl₃·7H₂O, Mg(NO₃)₂, and MnCl₂·4H₂O, were dissolved in deionized water and the previously synthesized Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst was stirred in their solutions for 4 h at 80 °C. Then the Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts were dried for 10 h at 110 °C. For conditioning, the

synthesized Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts were treated at 600 °C for 5 h in air. The metal content of the catalysts was measured by EDAX analysis (Fig. 1). The Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst has 4.82% nickel content. Result demonstrates that the nickel content of the catalysts was in the range of 3.73–4.02%, while the concentration of the second metals (Ca, Ce, La, Mg, Mn) was between 1.92% and 2.03% in case of Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst. More information about the catalysts are listed in other publication [21].

2.3. Pyrolysis process

The pyrolysis was carried out in a horizontal tubular furnace (Fig. 2). The reactor temperature was controlled by PID controller. Firstly, 5 g of raw materials and 2.5 g of the catalyst were placed in the reactor, separated by glass wool. When dolomite (10.0 g) was used, it was placed between the plastic sample and catalyst. In this work, two different temperatures were used: 550 °C and 850 °C. Nitrogen gas with a 2.5 dm³/h flow rate was used as a carrier gas and for providing inert atmosphere inside the reactor. After the reactor assembling, the temperature was elevated to the target temperature, then the reactor glass tube together with the raw material and catalyst was put into the furnace. The reaction time was 20 min. Then the reactor was disassembled, when the temperature reach the 300 °C. A Tedlar bag was used for collecting the gas productions, then gases were analysed by GC-TCD and GC-FID. On the other hand, volatiles from reactor were cooled by cryostat using 10 °C, where the pyrolysis oil was condensed. At the end of the reactions, products were weighted and their yields were calculated based on the weight balance.

2.4. Analysis of gas and liquid products

The composition of hydrocarbons in gases was measured by GC-FID (DANI GC) using Rtx PONA (100 m × 0.25 mm, surface thickness of 0.5 μm) and Rtx-5 PONA (100 m × 0.25 mm, surface thickness of 1 μm) columns. Sample analysis was taken using isotherm conditions (T = 30 °C).

Shimadzu GC-2010 gas-chromatograph equipped with TCD detector (CarboxenTM 1006 PLOT column (30 m × 0.53 mm)) was used to investigate the syngas product (hydrogen and carbon monoxide). The temperature was elevated from 35 °C (hold time 2 min) to 250 °C at 40 °C/min heating rate, with the final temperature maintained for 5 min.

Pyrolysis oil was analysed by DANI GC, using Rtx 1 dimetil-polysiloxan capillary column (30 m × 0.53 mm, thickness of 0.25 μm). Sample was heated to 40 °C for 5 min, then the temperature was elevated by 8 °C/min up to 340 °C and it was kept at 340 °C till 20min. Both the injector and detector temperature was

Fig. 1. The metal content of the catalysts (EDAX result).

Fig. 2. Process layout. (a-nitrogen, no dolomite, b-nitrogen and dolomite).

340 °C.

Carbon deposition on catalyst was analysed by temperature programmed oxidation (TPO). 250 mg of the catalysts were heated in air using thermogravimetric method by 10 °C/min heating rate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Product yields

In this work, various Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts were tested for syngas production by the pyrolysis-gasification of real waste polyolefin and PET mixtures using different reaction conditions. Fig. 3 summarizes the influence of catalysts, pyrolysis temperature, and atmosphere on the product yields, as well as carbon deposition

on the catalyst's surface. The data well demonstrates that the presence of catalyst has a positive effect on the gas yields compared to the catalyst-free pyrolysis-gasification. A clear increase was observed in the gas yield when the catalyst was used in the reactor. This effect can be attributed to the ability of the ZSM-5 catalyst supporter to redound the depolymerization and further break down of long polymer chain in raw materials into small molecules. Under nitrogen atmosphere, the maximum gas yield was 30.6% and 70.6% at temperatures of 550 and 850 °C respectively. Both of them were achieved by the using of Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst. The maximum gas yield with the addition of dolomite was 30.7% and 72.9% for the temperatures of 550 and 850 °C, respectively. It means that the dolomite presence did not affect the gas formation at 550 °C. Contrary to the before mentioned phenomena, the second metal

Fig. 3. Product yield. (a-nitrogen, no dolomite, 550 °C, b-nitrogen, no dolomite, 850 °C, c-nitrogen and dolomite, 550 °C, d-nitrogen and dolomite, 850 °C).

incorporation can increase the gas yield, because the maximum gas yield was observed not by the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst, but with Me/Ni/ZSM-5.

Similar results were found by He. M et al., who pyrolyzed municipal solid waste (MSW) at high temperature in the presence of dolomite [22]. Regarding the char, no significant effect of the catalysts was found. The char yield was in the range of 20.7–22.8% at 550 °C and 10.0–12.8% at 850 °C. Based on the results, it is clear that neither the presence of catalysts nor the use of dolomite had a significant effect on the char yield. However, the temperature was a key parameter to the char yield, because the amount of solids residues in the reactor was significantly lower at higher temperatures. For this phenomenon, the dominance of gasification reactions at 850 °C could be blamed. Therefore further decomposition of the degrading polymer blends in the reactor resulted in a reduction in the amount of char at higher temperatures as shown in equations (1) (2) and (3).

It is also well shown that the temperature, dolomite presence, and the second metal on the catalysts can obviously affect the carbonaceous deposition on the catalyst. In general, higher pyrolysis temperature led to a lower amount of deposited carbon on the catalyst surface. It was in the range of 12.3–16.2% at 550 °C, which decreased to 6.4–9.8% at 850 °C. As it was before mentioned, this was due to the gasification reactions at the higher temperatures.

The dolomite results similar significant decreasing in the carbon deposition at both temperatures. It means that the dolomite presence before the catalyst bed can transform the carbonaceous deposition to gases. The yield of solid depositions and char can also be decreased by an increase in temperature from 550 °C to 850 °C. Comparing the two temperatures, more significant reduction in char depositions on the catalyst's surface was observed at 850 °C, than at 550 °C. It is well known that CO₂ generates from dolomite at elevated temperatures (5) (6). However, more CO₂ can be generated from the dolomite at higher temperatures, than in lower temperatures. On one hand MgCO₃ produces CO₂ above 350–400 °C, but on the other hand, at lower temperatures due to its readsorption, less CO₂ can release.

This is the reason why the amount of coke could decrease to a greater extent at 850 °C than at 550 °C. In the former case, there was a higher concentration of CO₂ in the gas mixture in contact with the catalyst than in the gas mixture formed at 550 °C. The decrease in solid coke-rich deposition corresponds to the ability of carbon-dioxide for carbon reduction by the following reaction (6) [23].

In general, the metal incorporation to the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst results further decreases in the carbon deposition (especially at 550 °C). Regarding the second metals, the La and Ce showed the greatest activity in the reduction of deposited materials. On the other hand, Mn/Ni/ZSM-5, Ce/Ni/ZSM-5, and La/Ni/ZSM-5 revealed the highest gas yield among the other used catalysts in the carbon

dioxide atmosphere, which were 72.9, 72.5, and 72.2% at 550 °C, respectively. It was observed, that Ce and La can promote the C + CO₂ = 2CO reactions. It is important to remark, that this phenomenon could not be observed at 550 °C when the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst resulted in the highest gas yield, and the second metal incorporation reduced the gas yield in each case.

3.2. Gases

The compositions of gases measured by GC-TCD are shown in Fig. 4, while the calculated syngas yield are summarized in Table 1. Based on data, it is clear that the gases contain hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and methane, branched and linear hydrocarbons up to C₅.

It also appears that the H₂ and CO concentration in the gas product can increase with temperature both in the absence and presence of catalyst. However, the maximum H₂ and CO gas yields were achieved over La/Ni/ZSM-5 and Ce/Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst at the temperature of 850 °C. The H₂ and CO yield was 52.6% and 24.9% using La/Ni/ZSM-5 or 51.1% and 28.7% in the case of Ce/Ni/ZSM-5, respectively. The positive effect of Ce for syngas production was confirmed by Wu et al. [24]. Saad and Williams have reported that catalytic reforming temperature of 800 °C had the maximum yields of H₂ and CO for the pyrolysis of plastic waste (LDPE, HDPE, PS, PET and PP) [25]. Hydrocarbons at a high temperature can produce more hydrogen and carbon according to the following reaction:

Regarding the Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts, the lowest hydrogen concentration in the gas product (14.2%) was obtained in the presence of Mn/Ni/ZSM-5 at 550 °C exclusive of dolomite. Glancing the methane concentration, the data showed that gases obtained at 850 °C contain more methane, than that at 550 °C without dolomite. However opposite tendency was found when dolomite had been placed between the raw material and catalyst. To investigate the effect of the second metal on Ni/ZSM-5, it can be concluded, that they had a slight effect on the CH₄ concentration. The increase in methane concentration was attributed to the methanization reaction in the gas product:

Results also show that the atmosphere has a notable effect to the gaseous products when catalysts were used. Similar composition of gases was found at both temperatures comparing the pyrolysis with and without dolomite. However, a significant increase in syngas and CO₂ concentration was observed in the case of thermal pyrolysis-gasification followed by catalytic dry reforming. This result suggests that the presence of catalysts is essential for the positive effect of CO₂ on synthesis gas production. The increase in CO₂ concentration was the consequence of the calcination reactions of dolomite with the formation of CO₂. This CO₂ can further take place in dry reforming reactions. Hence, the increase in hydrogen and carbon monoxide was attributed to the reforming reactions in the carbon dioxide atmosphere:

This is in agreement with the results published by Saad et al., 2015 who found that pyrolysis of HDPE in the presence of CO₂ and high temperature could enhance the carbon dioxide reaction with hydrocarbons and resulting in more syngas yield [23]. In addition, Elbaba and Williams performed the pyrolysis of waste tires in the presence of dolomite and nickel catalyst. They reported

Fig. 4. Composition of gases.

(a-nitrogen, no dolomite, 550 °C, b-nitrogen, no dolomite, 850 °C, c-nitrogen and dolomite, 550 °C, d-nitrogen and dolomite, 850 °C).

Table 1

Syngas production, mmol/g.

		550 °C			850 °C		
		H ₂	CO	Syngas	H ₂	CO	Syngas
Nitrogen, no dolomite	No-catalyst	3.0	1.8	4.8	27.9	20.3	485.2
	Ni/ZSM-5	7.2	4.1	11.3	35.5	25.3	60.8
	Ca/Ni/ZSM-5	6.3	4.1	10.5	38.8	24.1	62.8
	Ce/Ni/ZSM-5	11.4	5.0	16.4	48.4	29.2	77.6
	La/Ni/ZSM-5	9.0	3.1	12.1	44.3	25.1	69.4
	Mg/Ni/ZSM-5	6.9	3.7	10.7	35.6	19.5	55.1
	Mn/Ni/ZSM-5	5.4	4.3	9.7	40.4	22.8	63.2
Nitrogen, with dolomite	No-catalyst	4.6	2.7	7.3	34.9	25.4	60.3
	Ni/ZSM-5	8.0	4.7	12.7	61.6	33.6	95.2
	Ca/Ni/ZSM-5	7.7	4.0	11.7	64.3	32.0	96.3
	Ce/Ni/ZSM-5	10.2	4.9	15.1	74.0	41.6	115.6
	La/Ni/ZSM-5	9.3	4.5	13.8	75.9	35.9	111.8
	Mg/Ni/ZSM-5	7.0	3.5	10.5	60.4	30.4	90.8
	Mn/Ni/ZSM-5	6.3	3.5	9.8	70.7	35.7	106.3

that syngas production was improved by the introduction of Ni into dolomite [26]. The calculated amounts of the syngas in mmol/g unit are summarized in Table 1.

In catalyst-free pyrolysis at a lower temperature, the syngas production was 4.8 mmol/g (3.0 mmol/g hydrogen and 1.8 mmol/g CO) without dolomite and 7.3 mmol/g (4.6 mmol/g hydrogen and 2.7 mmol/g CO) using dolomite. These values are increased to 48.2 mmol/g and 60.4 mmol/g at 550 °C and 850 °C, respectively. In one hand, it means, that the atmosphere has no significant effect on the syngas yield without catalysts. On the other hand, the positive effect of the CO₂ – obtained by the dolomite decomposition – on the synthesis gas production was clearly visible when catalysts

were used. Most catalysts had a positive effect on the syngas production because it was in the range of 9.7–16.4 mmol/g at 550 °C (without dolomite), 9.8–15.1 mmol/g at 550 °C (with dolomite), 55.1–77.6 mmol/g at 850 °C (without dolomite) and 90.8–115.6 mmol/g at 850 °C (with dolomite). Comparing the role of the second metals on the Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts, it can be shown that Ce and La had the most advantageous effect on both the hydrogen and CO increasing, while the Ca do not significantly affect the syngas production. Moreover, a lower amount of both hydrogen and CO in gases was measured when the Mg had been incorporated into the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst and used at 850 °C. It is worth to mention that this adverse effect could not observe at 550 °C.

Fig. 5. The ratio of C₂–C₅ branched and C₂–C₅ non-branched hydrocarbons.

The hydrocarbon composition of gases was followed by GC-FID. Gases contained hydrocarbons up to C₅. Fig. 5 shows the ratio of C₂–C₅ branched and C₂–C₅ non-branched hydrocarbons. Results well demonstrate the isomerisation effect of the catalysts. However, it is an interesting result, that the CO₂ presence had a positive effect to the formation of branched hydrocarbon at lower temperature. Lower ratio of C₂–C₅ branched and C₂–C₅ non-branched hydrocarbons were found in N₂–CO₂ atmosphere than in N₂ at 850 °C over Me/Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts.

3.3. Pyrolysis oils

The composition of pyrolysis oil was measured by GC-FID; results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. The liquid fraction of pyrolysis contained n-olefins, n-paraffin, non-oxygenated aromatics, branched, and oxygenated compounds. The results indicate that due to the high polyethylene content of raw materials (14% high-density polyethylene and 17% low-density polyethylene) the concentration of n-paraffin and n-olefin were high. Comparing the catalyst-free and thermo-catalytic pyrolysis, the higher concentration of non-branched aliphatic components was obtained without catalysts. On the other hand, the increased temperature can decrease a bit, while the CO₂ in the pyrolysis-gasification atmosphere can increase the n-paraffin and n-olefin content in pyrolysis oils. It is also well shown, that the second metal did not

affect the n-paraffin and n-olefin content.

Regarding to single ring aromatic compounds in the oil products, mainly benzene, toluene, ethyl-benzene, xylenes, benzene derivate were found. The results show that the amount of aromatic compounds has increased by the use of catalysts, while the single ring aromatic content has slightly decreased with increasing temperature. The increase in the amount of aromatics was caused by the aromatization reactions in the presence of the catalyst. In general, the presence of CO₂ during pyrolysis slightly reduced the amount of aromatics. It is an interesting observation that Ca, Ce, and La had a synergistic effect on the most prominent aromatization reactions, while the incorporation of Mg and Mn on the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst inhibited the aromatization reactions. This phenomenon could be observed both in the case of the nitrogen and the N₂+CO₂ atmosphere.

The oxygenated compounds in the oil were mainly represented in the form of phenol, benzoic acid, and terephthalic acid. The concentration of phenol and terephthalic acid was increased with increasing the temperature to 850 °C using nitrogen, while the opposite tendency was concluded in the N₂+CO₂ atmosphere. Glancing the effect of catalysts, an interesting result was observed. In nitrogen, the concentration of phenol and benzoic acid decreased by the use of catalysts at both temperatures. A similar tendency was observed regarding the terephthalic acid at 550 °C in N₂+CO₂, however, the catalysts incorporation of the second metal resulted in higher terephthalic acid concentration, especially in the case of Ca, Ce, and Mn at 850 °C. The presence of catalysts reduced the amount of phenol, terephthalic acid, and benzoic acid at 850 °C in each case using an N₂+CO₂ atmosphere comparing to pyrolysis-gasification in nitrogen. Similar tendency was found at 550 °C regarding the terephthalic acid and benzoic acid, but the concentration of phenol rather increased a bit especially by the using of catalysts at 550 °C. Metals on the catalyst can further reduce the phenol and terephthalic acid content in the case of Ca, Ce, and La (only for terephthalic acid) at 550 °C.

At 850 °C the second metals had no significant effect on the before-listed components. At 550 °C the Mg and Mn had well shown antagonistic effect to the decreasing of the benzoic acid level. Regarding the other oxygen-containing components, neither catalysts nor the second metals had any major effect at 850 °C in the case of both nitrogen and N₂+CO₂ atmosphere. At 550 °C the use of catalysts in nitrogen a bit increased the concentration of other oxygen-containing compounds, while opposite tendency was found in the N₂+CO₂ atmosphere.

Table 2

The composition of pyrolysis oils, area % (nitrogen).

		No-catalyst	Ni/ZSM-5	Ca/Ni/ZSM-5	Ce/Ni/ZSM-5	La/Ni/ZSM-5	Mg/Ni/ZSM-5	Mn/Ni/ZSM-5
550°C	n-paraffin	17.1	14.2	13.8	12.4	14.5	16.0	15.4
	n-olefin	19.9	15.6	14.6	14.4	16.5	18.1	17.8
	Single ring aromatic	6.0	10.4	12.4	16.0	12.8	7.5	8.5
	Multiring aromatic	2.4	5.5	6.0	7.4	6.4	7.5	6.3
	Oxygen containing	5.5	7.4	6.5	7.3	6.5	5.8	7.7
	Phenol	3.0	3.6	2.8	2.1	1.5	1.3	1.5
	Terephthalic acid	12.7	10.2	9.0	7.9	8.8	8.1	9.2
	Benzoic acid	13.1	10.7	10.2	8.6	8.8	12.5	12.5
	Other	20.3	22.5	24.8	23.9	24.1	23.2	21.1
	850°C	n-paraffin	10.4	9.7	8.5	8.9	8.6	8.9
n-olefin		11.9	10.9	9.5	9.5	9.1	9.5	9.7
Single ring aromatic		7.4	13.3	11.9	14.9	12.3	11.6	13.1
Multiring aromatic		10.5	8.4	8.2	7.7	9.1	9.4	9.2
Oxygen containing		6.7	7.0	5.3	5.8	6.7	5.3	5.3
Phenol		6.1	4.4	4.4	3.6	3.8	4.1	3.9
Terephthalic acid		13.1	13.4	16.2	18.0	15.6	14.7	17.0
Benzoic acid		15.3	6.8	6.8	5.2	5.8	6.5	5.8
Other		18.7	26.0	29.3	26.4	29.0	29.9	26.8

Table 3
The composition of pyrolysis oils, area % (nitrogen and dolomite).

		No-catalyst	Ni/ZSM-5	Ca/Ni/ZSM-5	Ce/Ni/ZSM-5	La/Ni/ZSM-5	Mg/Ni/ZSM-5	Mn/Ni/ZSM-5
550°C	n-paraffin	21.3	17.1	18.1	18.6	19.2	17.6	16.4
	n-olefin	22.6	18.4	18.8	19.5	19.5	18.2	16.9
	Single ring aromatic	4.6	7.9	10.3	10.7	8.6	5.1	4.1
	Multiring aromatic	2.9	5.0	5.7	6.0	6.4	6.9	7.1
	Oxygen containing	6.5	4.9	4.9	4.7	5.0	5.6	6.4
	Phenol	2.2	4.3	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.4	1.9
	Therephthalic acid	11.8	7.9	8.8	7.6	8.4	7.3	8.4
	Benzoic acid	14.7	8.8	6.5	6.5	7.5	11.0	11.6
	Other	13.3	25.8	24.9	24.4	22.4	25.0	27.1
850°C	n-paraffin	14.9	12.6	11.9	10.7	11.7	10.4	12.8
	n-olefin	16.2	13.9	12.6	10.7	12.1	10.5	13.3
	Single ring aromatic	6.7	10.1	10.8	12.0	10.7	12.0	13.0
	Multiring aromatic	8.2	15.3	14.3	15.9	16.1	17.6	12.9
	Oxygen containing	6.5	6.0	5.9	6.9	6.3	6.2	6.4
	Phenol	2.1	2.3	1.8	2.2	2.5	1.4	1.9
	Therephthalic acid	9.8	5.1	5.4	6.5	4.8	5.4	4.3
	Benzoic acid	11.1	6.5	6.4	7.0	6.3	7.1	6.6
	Other	24.5	28.1	31.0	28.2	29.6	29.4	28.8

3.4. Catalysts

One of the benefits for the waste polymer pyrolysis-gasification and pyrolysis-gasification-reforming is the possibility for the production of filamentous carbon deposition (carbon nanotubes

(CNT)). In general, temperature-programmed oxidation is widely used for the characterization of carbonaceous deposition as amorphous or filamentous. In this work, temperature-programmed oxidation (TPO) was used to characterize the type of carbon deposition on the catalyst's surface (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Carbon deposition on the catalysts. (a-nitrogen, no dolomite, 550 °C, b-nitrogen, no dolomite, 850 °C, c-nitrogen and dolomite, 550 °C, d-nitrogen and dolomite, 850 °C).

Fig. 7. Carbon nanotubes obtained from the catalyst surfaces.

(a-Ce/Ni/ZSM-5, 850 °C, no dolomite, b-Ce/Ni/ZSM-5, 850 °C, dolomite, c-Ni/ZSM-5, 850 °C, no dolomite, d-La/Ni/ZSM-5, 850 °C, no dolomite, e-La/Ni/ZSM-5, 850 °C, dolomite, f-Ce/Ni/ZSM-5, 550 °C, dolomite).

Filamentous and amorphous carbon types were formed on the catalyst from the pyrolysis of waste plastics at various temperatures and atmospheres. In general, the nitrogen atmosphere and higher temperature look better parameters for the filamentous carbon production. As it was discussed earlier, the higher temperature favours to the coke reduction from the catalyst surface. Catalysts had higher coke deposition at 550 °C than 850 °C. It was between 140 and 174 mg/g raw material at 550 °C and in the range of 123–160 mg/g raw material at 850 °C. Data showed that the proportion of amorphous carbons was much higher than filamentous carbons for all catalyst types at 550 °C. With the increase in the temperature to 850 °C, the proportion of amorphous carbons was decreased with an increase in the filamentous carbons. At higher temperature, the CO₂ has a disadvantageous role in the filamentous carbon production, because significantly lower ratio of filamentous/amorphous carbon was observed using dolomite, than that without dolomite. This observation was confirmed by Juniza Md Saad et al. who demonstrated that less filamentous carbon deposition was formed on the catalyst's surface during the HDPE plastic waste pyrolysis-reforming with the increasing proportion of CO₂ in the pyrolysis atmosphere [20]. On the other hand, Ce and La/Ni-ZSM-5 showed the most filamentous carbons at both temperatures. It is also clear, that the incorporation of the second metal on the Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts can increase the yield of filamentous carbon, because the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst resulted in the lowest filamentous/amorphous carbon ratio at both 550 and 850 °C with and without dolomite. This phenomenon refers to the enhanced catalyst activity of bimetallic catalysts in the formation of valuable carbonaceous deposition on the catalyst. The addition of dolomite to the process resulted in a slight change at low temperature, and increasing of the amorphous part at 850 °C.

Fig. 7 shows the carbonaceous materials obtained from the surface of the catalysts. The TEM results show the formation of tubular filamentous carbon. The diameter of multi-walled carbon nanotubes was less than 20 nm. In cases where a higher proportion of amorphous carbon was determined by TPO (f), darker spots were visible on the images. This was due to the higher proportion of amorphous carbon.

4. Conclusion

In this study, different metal/Ni-ZSM-5 catalysts were synthesized in order to improve the production of syngas from waste plastics (LDPE, HDPE, PP, PET, and others). H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, and hydrocarbons up to C₆ were the main components in the gases, while n-paraffin, n-olefin, oxygenated, branched and aromatics compounds were mainly in the pyrolysis oil. The yields and compositions of gases were greatly influenced by the reaction temperature, catalyst, and presence of dolomite. The incorporation of Ce on Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst had a positive effect on waste plastic decomposition and increases the syngas production. On the other hand, the catalyst of Mg/Ni/ZSM-5 showed less amounts of syngas. The in-situ carbon-dioxide production from dolomite resulted in a marked increase of syngas production and decreased carbon deposition on the catalyst surface at a temperature of 850 °C. It was found that the amount of oil product was higher for the process without catalyst. TPO was used to characterize the catalyst and measure the produced carbon. The amount and type of deposited carbon was greatly influenced by the atmosphere and catalyst composition. The highest yields of carbons were formed at 550 °C. The dolomite had a negative role in the production of filamentous carbons, especially at the higher temperature.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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